

Violence Against Women, Factors And Effects From The Point Of View Of Members Of Family Reform Offices In Sharia Courts

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This study aimed to identify violence against women, and its most important effects from the point of view of members of family reform offices in Sharia courts in Jordan. The study sample consisted of (50) members, and to achieve the aim of the study, a questionnaire was developed that consisted in its final form of (19) items. The results showed that the most common factor of violence against women is the growth of the individual in a violent environment, Where this paragraph was an average of (4.33), and the great cultural difference between the spouses, especially if the wife is the highest cultural level, generates tension and imbalance in the husband as a reaction to him, and thus resorting to violence and is the second most important factor that leads to violence against women Where the study sample agreed to this with a mean of (4.16). As for the most important consequences of violence against women, which is the woman's physical deformities as a result of violence that hinder her from practicing her normal life, and the average for this paragraph is (4.15), The study sample also showed that violence affects those who are practiced around them, such as sons and brothers or sisters, with an average of (4.02). Among the effects that the study sample unanimously agreed upon is that violence may prevent women from continuing their education and advancing their intellectual level with an average of (3.99).</i></p> <p><i>As for the position of Islam in limiting the phenomenon of violence against women and its effects, the study showed that Islam guaranteed a woman her financial independence, so men have no right to take possession of her own money. with a average of (4.04), and a paragraph that (permits Islam for a woman to prevent a man from the rights she is bound to in the marriage contract) showed, he deprived her of some of her rights, such as alimony and others, with a average of (3.85).</i></p>
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Introduction

The phenomenon of violence against women in the world has received great attention as a result of the repeated attacks and crimes against women in most societies of the world, through seminars, lectures and workshops calling for the importance and respect of women, hence the family is the basic structure in the social structure of society and on this basis it must prevail Affection, compassion, love and trust between spouses because of its positive effects on the upbringing of children, and the opposite of that may lead to domestic violence, displacement of children and give them aggressive behaviors towards their parents and society. Here, the righteous family should enjoy Islamic education because of its many advantages and benefits in providing its members with purposeful behaviors and ethics that are bad from the psychological, social, emotional and other aspects, especially in our time that is characterized by the tension of family and social relations between the spouses and the exit of the woman to work as a result of the economic situation The deteriorating and exposing the family to openness due to the spread of technology and modern means of communication such as satellite channels, computers and mobile phones that may sometimes be encouraged to commit violence, crime, and behaviors that are contrary to Islamic law and the Arab and international community, Hence, Islamic education and social and educational upbringing may seek concern for the family in order to prepare a healthy family in order to create and prepare a generation that is aware and educated in the educational, social, moral and religious system of individuals characterized by a civilized personality. then we find that the most important goals of an individual's education and his upbringing within a family characterized by good values and morals is to "modify and develop the individual's behaviors, attitudes and ethics in such a way that it is compatible with societal behaviors and ethics." (Moses, 1998 AD). Finally, this research will clarify violence against women and the factors and effects of that from the point of view of the study sample represented by members of family reform offices of both sexes.

1. study Problem:

The problem of the study lies in the increase in the perpetration of forms of violence against women in all societies, as most women are subjected to beatings, rape, abuse and insults without leaving any consideration to women, whether from a religious, social, psychological, physical, or emotional aspect, and that this violence against women may have negative effects on all Family members who work in the end to destroy society, weaken coherence and achieve security among individuals. Despite the large number researches and studies that talked about the issue of violence against women, but these studies did not refer to the role of religion in general and Islam in particular in reducing the phenomenon of violence against women because failure to follow the foundations of religious and moral education within the family may create various forms of violence against women. Hence, the study problem is defined by explaining violence against women and its great role in the upbringing and care of the generation.

2. Study questions:

1. What are the most important factors of violence against women?
2. What are the main effects of violence against women?
3. What is the position of Islam in reducing the phenomenon of violence against women?

3. Study objective:

- 1- Identify the most important factors leading to violence against women.
- 2- Knowing the most important effects of violence against women.
3. Identify the position of Islam from the phenomenon of violence against women.

4. The importance of study

The importance of the study in theory is that it searches for the most important factors leading to violence against women, its various problems, its negative effects and its danger on the family and society. It also seeks to present a theoretical framework in general about the role of Islam and religion in reducing the phenomenon of violence and crime against women. In practice, the results of this study may help in planning the development of preventive, curative and advisory programs with an ethical, educational, social and religious concept that benefit the family in order to reduce the negative effects on the individual and society. The importance of this study also emerges from the lack of studies and research on the position of Islam in particular, religion in general, and domestic violence and methods of treatment.

5. Study limitations:

- 1- The time limit: The study is limited to violence against women, the factors and effects from the point of view of members of the family reform offices in the Sharia courts, the second semester of the academic year 2019.
- 2- Place and Objective Limit: This research is limited to determining violence against women, factors and effects from the point of view of members of family reform offices in Sharia courts, from the point of view of the study sample.
- 3- The human limit: This research is limited to members of family reform offices in Sharia courts.
- 4- The results of the study are determined by the nature of the tool and its validity and reliability indications.

6. Procedural terminology:

- **Violence:** "Behaviors outside the laws and regulations emanating from individuals or groups, and these behaviors are characterized by hostility, It aims to harm oneself or others, or property. Whether this damage is material or moral.
- **Violence against women:** "Behaviors outside the laws and regulations practiced by men against women. These behaviors are hostile and may be psychological, physical, social or economic behavior, which may hurt her feelings and lose her respect in society."
- **Family reform:** treatment marital disputes between the two parties without resorting to Sharia and judicial courts to the satisfaction of both parties and guarantee their rights.
- **Family reform offices:** they are offices established in the Sharia courts in Jordan called the offices of family reform, mediation and reconciliation aims at family counseling, preventive, curative, and developmental for the treatment of family union and continuity, and treatment family disputes.

7. Theoretical framework and previous studies:

Violence in the Arabic language: By joining the eye and the silence of the noon: hardship, and lack of compassion in the matter, which is against kindness, and all that is good in kindness, in violence is evil like it. (Ibn Manzur, 1986).

Violence idiomatically: Is the use of pressure or force is an illegal or unlawful use that affects the will of an individual. (Badawi, 1978).

Violence is also defined as: A behavior performed by an individual (or group of individuals) with the aim of causing harm or harm to another individual (or group of individuals) who tries to avoid this physical harm. he was (materially) or psychologically (intangible) or the object of his property. (Abdullah, 2009).

violence against Woman: It is "the behavior or action directed at women in particular, whether they are a wife, mother, sister or daughter, and is characterized by varying degrees of discrimination, persecution, oppression

and aggression resulting from unequal power relations between women and men in society and the family alike, as a result of the control of the patriarchal system." With its economic, social and cultural mechanisms. " (Abdel-Wahhab, 2000).

Family reform offices: They are special sections within the Sharia courts that aim to end family disputes in friendly ways and awareness and education of marital rights and duties, and providing family counseling (Regulation No. 17 of 2017 of the Code of Sharia Procedures).

8.1 Islam's position on violence against women

Islam has given women great attention by taking pride in and honoring them, and has considered them to be the mother, sister, wife, grandmother, and man's partner in life

To take responsibility and his participation in sustainable development in society and parenting. The Islamic religion calls people and members of society through enjoining good and forbidding evil, respecting and preserving women and preserving their rights. God said: (O mankind! reverence your Guardian-Lord, who created you from a single person, created, of like nature, His mate, and from them twain scattered (like seeds) countless men and women; - reverence Allah, through whom ye demand your mutual (rights) , and (reverence) the wombs (That bore you): for Allah ever watches over you).(almisa: 1). And in a hadith by the Messenger (women are the sisters of men), he forbade insulting women and ordered that they be treated with kindness and mercy. The Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, stresses that in the farewell pilgrimage and says in his famous sermon: (Take good care of women, for they will help you). And through these noble verses and noble prophetic hadiths, Islam raised the status of women and honored them with the right to breastfeeding, care, good education, the right to education, education, work, ownership and sale in a manner that does not violate the law of Islam. Among the forms of Islam honoring women is that it forbade the husband to strike his wife without justification and gave her the right to complain about her matter to her guardian or the ruler because she is considered a person with dignity and respect. And in a hadith of the Prophet (No one of you flogs his wife flogging a servant, then he sleeps with her) narrated by Bukhari and Muslim. Islam indicated that there is no preference for a male over a female, or versa, in favor of piety and good deeds, through the Qur'an verse: (O mankind! We created you from a single (pair) of a male and a female, and made you into nations and tribes, that ye may know each other (not that ye may despise (each other). Verily the most honoured of you in the sight of Allah is (he who is) the most righteous of you. And Allah has full knowledge and is well acquainted (with all things)). (Al-Hujraat: 13). This means that Islam has preceded many contemporary and international legislation on the issue of equality between the sexes by at least 1000 years, especially the historic declaration of the United Nations General Assembly regarding women and human rights (all people are born free and equal in dignity and rights and this is on November 10, 1948).

8.2 Violence in Jordanian society

Jordanian society is considered a patriarchal society characterized by the sovereignty of men, who derive their strength and authority from the inherited social values and norms that give the greatest role to men in the spheres of life. The manifestations of violence begin at the beginning of the birth of the female, when signs of dissatisfaction appear on the man's face, then the process of socialization in Jordanian society begins in terms of sexual discrimination in granting the male greater freedom than the female in the field of education, learning, work, play and forming social relationships. Marriage to a girl is considered her only concern as it preserves and protects her, and parents may resort to marrying their daughters early because some of them consider them to be their concern for education, food, clothing and so on, and their marriage is characterized by violence in robbing them of their freedom by choosing the husband, especially in rural and Bedouin areas. Although Islam gave women the right to choose a spouse, and that the majority of Jordanian society owes Islam, which is a source of their behavior, social relations, rulings and legislation. (Al-Awawdah, 2009).

With the cultural, social, economic and political changes that have taken place in the world in general, and Jordan in particular, it has made tangible progress in reducing the practice of violence against women. The contribution of women to the labor market ranges between 12-28%. Despite this, these percentages are considered low compared to other societies. Jordanian women suffer from taking administrative positions in decision-making, especially in the political and administrative sphere, but the political changes brought about by His Majesty King Abdullah II Ibn Al Hussein and Her Majesty Queen Rania have promote the participation of women in taking higher administrative positions and the quota system in the Jordanian Parliament, to be A starting point, and promote Jordanian women to engage in political, social and administrative life, and so that the members of the Jordanian society accept the idea of women participating with them in building society in all different fields (Abu Ghazaleh, 2009).

Jordan is one of the developed countries in combating violence, through civil society and governmental institutions, in dealing with the problem of violence against women and its impact. Through targeted, developed programs that help women avoid violence, given that these programs are of a high level compared to other societies. At the present time, the "Telephone Counseling" program of the Jordanian Women's Union has been launched, and it is one of the few programs in the Arab world specialized in this regard. Governmental interest

in the issue of violence against women is also evident through a number of projects that work to confront violence, including the establishment of the National Council for Family Affairs headed by Her Majesty Queen Rania Al-Abdullah, and the establishment of the “Family Protection Department” of the Public Security Directorate. (El Harrasha, 2007).

8.3 Factors leading to violence against women

Social factors: The behavior of the individual may be shaped in the light of social values and cultural norms that the individual learns during his life in the society in which he lives. Culture, customs and traditions are part of the process of socialization and it is important in the lives of community members. Children during childhood watch their families how their fathers deal with their mothers from While watching TV programs of criminal behavior and violence. Social upbringing may inculcate in the souls of children and the individual cultural beliefs and traditions such as teaching a young boy that he is the strongest and that the girl is the weakest and he is always responsible for it. Which leads to this belief in the creation of a generation that views women with a look of weakness and humiliation, and this increases the woman's sense of shame, fear, lack of defense and confidence in front of her friends and relatives in the workplace, school and home. (Ryan, 2008).

Economic factors: The shrinking of the economic situation, poverty, unemployment and low income for the family lead to the practice of violent crimes, murder and theft, especially on the part of the father, who is considered responsible for providing for the basic needs of the wife and children. As a result of economic and psychological suffering, emptiness, boredom and despair, which reflects negatively on children and wives, and sometimes the same situation is generated by the wife as a result of her passing through the same bad economic conditions, and the difficult economic situation of some families results in economic and social instability and thus the failure to provide basic needs for their members, which leads to conflict Between the husband and his wife to provide for the needs of the house, The conflict may develop into a kind of violent quarrel and beatings, and this violence is often on the part of the husband against his wife, and on the part of the father against his children, and some sons may beat their fathers in order to obtain money or buy what they do not have of basic needs. (Zaki, 2017). Violence and crime against women in its various forms is spread in all classes of society and at economic, social and cultural levels, and to varying degrees.

Psychological factors: The pressures and emotions resulting from the nature of work, the family, unemployment, economic conditions and the failure to meet the requirements of the basic needs of the family, make them live under social, economic and psychological pressure, and a feeling of failure, frustration, anxiety and a weak sense of responsibility towards family members. It causes the practice of aggressive behaviors and forms against his wife to get rid of these tensions and emotions. (Abu Hazeem, 2017).

Sexual intercourse: Violence between men and women may be the result of not satisfying sexual desires, and cultural and social values may play a prominent role in determining the sexual role of both sexes. These sexual conflicts lead to aggressive behaviors and violence against women, especially in a society in which men dominate women. The difference in personality between men and women in terms of mental and age thinking may lead to a misconception in the psychology of each of them and weaken the process of sexual intercourse between the sexes. (Hussein, 2007).

8.4 Effects of violence against women

Social effects: Social effects include the cultural and social customs, traditions, beliefs, values and norms that society is accustomed to practicing and which considers violence and cruelty to be a characteristic of a man's characteristics and manhood. The difference in age, economy, and education between spouses, bad friends, and family interference in a wrong way between spouses, and the lack of knowledge of both husband and wife the rights of the other, such as obedience to the husband and leaving without his permission, and suspicion, insecurity and self-confidence of the husband and wife, and belief in myths, all lead This leads to an increase in violence against women, such as imposing isolation on the wife by not visiting family and friends, engaging in social relations and practicing work. (Deif Allah, 2010).

Economic effects: The bad economic situation in the family may lead to cruelty and violence on the part of the father on his family as a result of the psychological situation, emptiness, boredom and despair, which will reflect negatively on the children and wives, and sometimes the same situation is born for the wife as a result of her passing through the same bad economic conditions, and the difficult economic situation results in not providing The needs of the family, which leads to a struggle between the husband and his wife to provide for the needs of the home, and the conflict may develop into a kind of quarrels and violent beatings, and this violence often takes place on the part of the husband against his wife, and from the father on his children, and some children may beat their fathers in order to obtain Make money or buy what they do not have of basic needs. Poverty is considered one of the motives of violence against women, economic and social, and that is the result of the feeling of deprivation and imperfection of the poor, and these aggressive feelings arise from the conviction of these classes that their rights are lost. Studies indicate that there is a strong relationship between poverty and violence against women, sometimes reaching an assault on the lives of family members (Deif Allah, 2010).

Psychological effects: Violence against women may generate psychological effects on them such as fear, abuse, beatings, despair, deep sadness, crying, isolation, feelings of worthlessness and self-contempt, and as a result of

these negative effects, they may sometimes resort to drinking alcohol or taking drugs, suicide or violence against the husband or children in order to escape Of the problems you suffer from. (Zughayer, 2010).

8. Previous studies

a study . Kaloudi, et. al (2017), this study aimed to identify the effects surrounding violence in the family, in addition to knowing its causes and ways to reduce it, as violent behavior can cause problems when it is directed towards others with the aim of hurting them, and that violent behavior and crime related to the behavior has a role in The occurrence of major problems in social cohesion and public health, the results of the study showed that environmental factors and social and cultural factors play an important role in the development of violent behavior, and that violence within the family is the most silent crime in the world and has an impact on family and social life and can extend its impact on men and women The deprivation of the human being of his or her basic rights is considered in the context of violence between family members.

Study .da Silva, et. al (2017). entitled "Violence within the family", this study aimed to find out the causes, effects and consequences of violence in the family. It also aimed to present cases of violence against women, children and adolescents who were treated in the specialized reference center for social assistance, where this study is classified as a descriptive and documentary study, a sample of (800) reviewers were selected in the medical records. The research tool dealt with the socio-demographic variables chosen for the victims and the aggressors and the type of violence. Analyzing it with descriptive statistics and using the publication of the SPSS 22 program, and among the most important results of the study: Most of those who were exposed to violence were children and adolescents more than women, and that abuse often occurs from men, and that the low level of education is the main cause of violence within the family, and that violence is practiced. In all its forms within the family, be it sexual, physical or psychological. Study Subramaniam & Zulkarnain (2017), this study aimed to know the problems that may be caused by violence in the family, its effects and consequences, and it aimed to know its causes and consequences, as it was found from the results of the study that family violence is a health and social problem on a large scale. Women are the direct victims, but it turns out that children are also exposed to a great deal of violence within the family, and the study showed that there are significant destructive changes in the behaviors of children who are exposed to violence at home, where the most important of them were some of the main problematic behaviors that were identified are intransigence, irritability, arguments, emotional numbness and crying.

Study Al-Hiyasat (2016), this study aimed to find out the causes and forms of violence against the wife in the Jordanian society, and the study population consisted of battered women who were subjected to violence through a formal complaint against their husbands in the regions of the capital, Amman, and the study population consisted of abused wives in the capital, Amman. An intentional sample of (155) battered wives at the role of the Family Protection Department, and the SPSS statistical analysis program was used to reach the goals and objectives of this study; The most prominent results of this study were as follows: The highest percentage of women subjected to violence are those with low incomes, and most women who are subjected to violence are married to low-income husbands, and that the most prevalent form of violence is sexual violence, followed by physical violence, followed by psychological violence, and that one of the most important reasons behind the problem of violence against the wife is the low level of family income, and then the husband's distraction in social media, and the interference of the husband's family in the wife's marital life. The Family Protection Department for battered women, and specialists to deal with cases of violence against women, as well as awareness-raising and counseling sessions for battered women.

Sultan's study (2015) This study aimed to identify violence against rural women in the Assiut governorate in Egypt in terms of the causes of violence against them and their reaction, and to know the effects of this violence on them and their children, as well as to identify the methods and means to reduce violence against women and to achieve the goal of the study, data were collected. Of the (122) women who have cases in the Family Court in Assiut Governorate, the results summarized the presence of physical violence to a large extent among women in all its forms, as well as psychological, economic and sexual violence, the methods of violence that drive men to practice varied, including customs and traditions, weakness of a man's personality, interference by family, crying and leaving the house and going to the family are among the most important forms of a woman's reaction, so sadness, crying and lack of self-confidence were among the most important negative effects on the wife. The forms of violence between members of her family also varied in terms of discrimination between boy and girl in treatment and deprivation of education, early marriage, forced marriage. The results also indicated that violence occurs in transportation, streets, hospitals, and government institutions. Study Saad's (2015), this study aimed to know the effects of violence against women in the workplace, whether governmental or private, by showing the concepts related to that and pictures of violence against women in the workplace. This study dealt with violence against women in all its forms, regardless of where It was committed from a legislative perspective, without neglecting the international framework that dealt with this issue, the study found a set of results, the most important of which are: that violence against women has social, psychological and economic consequences as well, and that violence against women destroys the structure of society and the cohesion of society. A Shawasha study (2011) aimed at identifying the psychological and social needs of battered women in

Amman, where the study sample reached (204) women, and a questionnaire was developed with two standardized tools to identify needs and a semi-open interview. The results found that the availability of psychological and social needs of the battered women was average, and that economic problems are the most common problems that women suffer, then psychological and legal, and that the most used methods for women to confront violence are objection and discussion, and the complaint method in the security center was the least used, and that satisfaction Women about the services provided in the women's security center was of a medium degree.

What distinguishes the study from previous studies: Previous studies talked about the different types of violence against women and the factors that lead to it, such as the study (Sultan 2015, Al-Hisas 2016). The studies also showed the most important effects that violence against women has in society, whether on the woman herself or on her family members, whether she is a wife, son, or Others, such as the study (Kaloudi, et. Al 2017, Saad 2015). The current study agreed with most of the studies on the factors that drive men to use violence against women, such as the study (Subramaniam & Zulkarnain 2017, Shawasrah 2011). This study was distinguished from previous studies on the position of Islam in limiting the phenomenon of violence against women through the study sample.

9. Method and procedures

10.1 Study methodology: The researcher followed the descriptive and analytical approach to conduct this study, due to its relevance to the nature of the study.

10.2 Study community: The study community consisted of members of the family reform offices in Irbid, Ajloun and Jerash.

10.3 The study sample: A random sample of (50) members of the family reform offices was selected. It is as follows:

Distribution of study sample individuals according to demographic variables:

Table (1) Distribution of the study sample according to demographic variables

Variable	Categories	Iteration	Percentage
Sex	Male	23	46%
	Females	27	54%
Age	Less than 30 years	12	24%
	31-45 years	22	44%
	More than 45 years	16	32%
Experience	Less than 3 years	9	18%
	4-5 years	22	44%
	More than 5 years	19	38%
reform office	Irbid	20	40%
	Jarash	18	36%
	Ajloun	12	24%

9.4 Study tool: The researcher used the survey method to prepare questions to form the axes on which the questionnaire relied, which was applied to a number of members of family reform offices in order to identify violence against women. Where a questionnaire was developed to detect violence against women, after reviewing the theoretical literature on the subject of the study and previous studies. Which relates to the subject of the study tool and the number of paragraphs of the questionnaire in its final form was (19) paragraphs. The level of the answer for each paragraph was also graded according to the five-point Likert scale and defined by five levels as follows: Very agree and give (5) grades and the level of agreement and give (4) grades and a neutral level and give (3) grades and the level of disagreement and give (2) two grades and a level that strongly disagrees, and gives (1) one degree.

9.5 Tool validity: To verify the validity of the tool, the researcher relied on the validity of the content, as she presented the tool to a number of arbitrators who are specialized in the field of sociology, legitimate science, science and education, with the aim of knowing what the paragraphs measure from the required performance, and the relevance of the scale paragraphs to the variable to be measured, and to judge the paragraphs Its formulation, clarity, and relevance to the fields.

10.6 Tool stability: The values of stability coefficients (Cronbach alpha) were extracted for the fields of study and for the instrument as a whole, and they were as follows:

Table (2)
Evaluate the stability coefficients (Cronbach alpha) for the study domains

Domain	Stability factor
Factors of violence against women	0.66
The effects of violence against women	0.71
Islam's position in reducing the phenomenon of violence against women	0.64
The tool as a whole.	0.62

The results of the study showed an increase in the ratios of stability coefficients, which indicates a high consistency between the paragraphs of the same field separately and the paragraphs of the tool as a whole. This makes it acceptable for scientific research purposes.

10.7 Study procedures: After confirming the validity of the study tool and determining the sample to be applied to the questionnaire, the questionnaire was distributed to the study sample after explaining its objectives and asking the sample to fill it accurately and objectively. The researchers also assured the individuals included in the study that their answers will be treated with complete confidentiality, and that it will only be used for research purposes Scientific only, and respondents will be given, sufficient time to answer.

10.8 Statistical treatment: For the purpose of answering the research questions and achieving the desired goals, the following statistical treatments were used:

1. To answer the first, second, and third questions, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted, and the frequencies and percentages were extracted for the purposes of enumerating the sample.
2. To extract the stability of the tool, the stability factor (Cronbach Alpha) was used.

11. Results

To answer the first question, which states "What are the most important factors of violence against women?" The arithmetic averages and standard deviations were extracted for the answers of the study sample individuals with regard to the first domain, and the results were according to the following table (3):

No	Paragraph	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Rank	Grade
7	Growing up the individual in a violent environment Increase the probability of violence in old age.	4.33	1.02	1	high
6	The great cultural difference between the spouses, especially if the wife is culturally the highest level, generates tension and imbalance in the husband as a reaction to him, and therefore resort to violence.	4.16	1.04	2	high
2	The lack of access to women increases their probability of violence.	4.12	0.95	3	high
8	Environmental problems that put pressure on human beings may affect their behaviour and orientation towards violence	4.11	0.98	4	high
(1)	Women's acceptance and tolerance increase violence.	3.96	0.85	5	high
5	A wrong understanding of the male guardianship principle increases the practice of violence against women.	3.78	1.06	6	high
4	The prevailing culture in Arab societies, considering them to be male societies, contributes to the increase of violence against women.	3.64	0.79	7	high
3	Women's ignorance of their rights and duties is a main factor in their exposure to violence.	3.55	0.97	8	high
9	Economic problems and poverty are among	3.45	0.89	9	high

	the most important factors that lead individually to violence against women.				
College degree		3.90	0.66		high

It appears from the previous table that the arithmetic averages were high for the items according to the answers of the individuals of the study sample. The total arithmetic mean came (3.90), and with a standard deviation of (0.66).

The previous table shows that Paragraph No. (7) which states "Growing up in a violent environment increases the likelihood of engaging in violence in old age," came in first place with an arithmetic average of 4.33, while Paragraph No. 6 which states that On the "great cultural difference between spouses, especially if the wife is of the highest cultural level, generates tension and imbalance in the husband as a response to him, and thus resorting to violence" in the second rank with an arithmetic average of (4.16), and it came in the next-to-last rank, paragraph No. (3) which states that "a woman's ignorance of her rights and duties is a major factor in her exposure to violence," with an average arithmetic of (3.55), and paragraph No. (9) came in the last rank, which states: "Economic problems and poverty are among the most important factors that lead an individual to violence. Against women," with a mean of (3.45).

To answer the second question, which states "What are the most important consequences of violence against women?" The arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted for the answers of the study sample individuals, and the results in Table (4) were as follows:

No	Paragraph	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Rank	Grade
13	The woman may be infected Physical abnormalities As a result of violence, it prevent her from practicing her normal life.	4.15	1.1	1	high
14	Violence affects around them, such as children, brothers or sisters.	4.02	1.08	2	high
11	Violence may prevent women from pursuing their education and advancement at their intellectual level.	3.99	0.83	3	high
10	Women with mental illness are more likely to become mentally ill.	3.67	1.08	4	high
12	The spread of the concept of violence increases the distinction of society between males and females in financial wages	3.45	0.68	5	high
College degree		3.86	0.71		high

It appears from the previous table that the arithmetic averages were high for the items according to the answers of the individuals of the study sample, and the total arithmetic mean came (3.86), with a standard deviation of (0.71).

The previous table shows that Paragraph No. (13), which states that "a woman may suffer physical deformities as a result of violence that hinders her from practicing her normal life," came in first place with an arithmetic average of (4.15), while each of Paragraph No. (14) which states that On "Violence affects those who are practiced around them, such as sons, brothers or sisters" in the second rank with an arithmetic mean of (4.02), and the next-to-last rank came in Paragraph No. (10), which states: It reached (3.67), and came in the last rank Paragraph No. (12), which states "the spread of the concept of violence increases the distinction of society between males and females in the financial wage," with an average of (3.45).

To answer the third question, which states "What is the position of Islam in limiting the phenomenon of violence against women and its effects?" The arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted for the answers of the study sample individuals, and the results in Table (5) were as follows:

No	Paragraph	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Rank	Grade
15	Islam guarantees women their material independence and men do not have to seize their own money.	4.04	0.99	1	high
18	Islam allows women to prevent men from their rights to marriage, if they are deprived of certain rights such as maintenance, etc.	3.85	1.1	2	high

16	Islam does not allow men to engage in any form of violence against women.	3.75	0.86	3	high
19	Islam asserts that no one has jurisdiction over women if they are a rational and independent adult in managing their own affairs.	3.7	0.97	4	high
17	In Islamic law, women can swap violence against men as self-defense.	3.55	1.25	5	high
College degree		3.78	0.69		high

It appears from the previous table that the arithmetic averages were high for the items according to the answers of the individuals of the study sample, and the total arithmetic mean came (3.78), with a standard deviation of (0.69).

The previous table shows that Paragraph No. (15), which states that "Islam guarantees a woman her financial independence, so that a man cannot take possession of her own money," came in first place with an arithmetic average of (4.04), while Paragraph No. (18) came which states: "Islam permits A woman has the right to prevent a man from the rights she is bound to in the marriage contract, if he deprives her of some of her rights, such as maintenance and so on. There is no guardianship over a woman if she is an adult, rational and independent in managing her own affairs, with an average arithmetic average of (3.70), and Paragraph No. (17) came in the last rank. Which states, "In Islamic law, women can exchange violence against men as self-defense," with a average of (3.55).

12. Discussing the results:

The study sample showed that the most common factor for violence against women is growing up in a violent environment that increases the likelihood of engaging in violence in old age, as the study sample unanimously agreed on that with a average of (4.33), the great cultural difference between the spouses, especially if the wife is the highest cultural level, creates tension and imbalance in the husband as a response to him, and thus resorting to violence is one of the second most important factors that lead to violence against women, as the study sample agreed to this with a arithmetic average of (4.16).The study sample also showed that one of the most important of these effects is that a woman may suffer physical deformities as a result of violence that prevent her from practicing her normal life, with a mean of (4.15), the study sample also showed that violence affects those who are practiced around them, such as sons, brothers or sisters, with an average of (4.02). Among the effects that the study sample unanimously agreed upon is that violence may prevent women from continuing their education and advancing their intellectual level, with an average of (3.99).With regard to the position of Islam in reducing the phenomenon of violence against women and its effects, the answers of the study sample showed that Islam guarantees a woman her financial independence, so a man cannot seize her own money with an average of (4.04). In the marriage contract, he deprived her of some of her rights, such as maintenance and so on, with a average of (3.85).

13. Recommendations:

1. Preparing strategies, programs, and remedial and preventive methods that include how to deal with women who have been subjected to violence by husbands.
2. Encouraging governmental, civil and religious centers and institutions to hold seminars, lectures and workshops aimed at resolving family disputes related to violence against women, and to provide legal and legislative advice on their rights, such as family reform offices in Sharia courts.
3. Modification rules and regulations in line with the requirements of contemporary human life and keeping pace with modern developments as a result of social and cultural change that helps women protect them from violence.
4. Activating the role of the various media outlets by holding educational and guiding educational programs that show men and women the rights and duties of each of them, especially those who are about to get married.
5. Work to instill confidence in the soul of women by granting them their political rights, such as participation in parliament, economic, social, educational and administrative positions, such as holding senior managerial and leadership positions in the state and others.
6. Conducting more in-depth research and studies on the factors that push men to use violence against women in society and providing solutions to reduce the use of the phenomenon of violence.
7. Activating the role of the socialization process through the family and school by not distinguishing between male and female and respecting each other (husband and wife) because children by their nature imitate their parents how they behave inside the home.

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